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“MIGHTY FINI”

In front of the house is a pond.
The water is still and clear;
Plenty of fish swim, jump, and blend.
Happy to see them draw each other without fear.

Suddenly, the rain poured down as hard as it is.
I saw one fish swim with speed and ease;
To the top of the troubled water;
This type is more rigid than the other.

As I watched that little fish, I thought to name it “Fini”,
The mighty “Fini,” the slimy one with the tiny brain;
Can do things with a great range of skill in a game,
Tough to go beyond its capacity to swim to the top;
Take some time to breathe air,
Aggressively care to be saved.